

[For MontiSim please click here](#)

EmbeddedMontiArc: Textual Modeling Alternative to Simulink

(Tool Demonstration)

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EmbeddedMontiArc

Modeling Language for Cyber-Physical Systems

[Download EmbeddedMontiArcStudio 1.7.5-beta](#)

Portable App for Windows 64-bit

The paper uses the 1.7.5-beta version, and thus this is frozen at this page. Please, take a look at <http://embeddedmontiarc.com> for newer releases and further information about EmbeddedMontiArc.

Supplementary Material for Tool Demonstration:

[C&C Models](#)

[Screenshots of EmbeddedMontiArcStudio](#)

[Videos](#)

C&C Models

- Autopilot Model
 - graphical C&C Model; layout is automatically generated (Please pay attention to the three different abstraction levels when browsing the models in a new tab)
 - [Open Graphical Model](#)
 - [Youtube Video how the car is driving](#)
- ObjectDetector model with SpectralClusterer subcomponents
 - graphical C&C Model; layout is automatically generated
 - [Open Graphical Model](#)
 - [Published Textual EmbeddedMontiArc Model](#)
 - [Execute Model in Web-Browser \(Browser needs WebAssembly support\)](#)
- PacMan
 - graphical C&C Model; layout is automatically generated
 - [Open Graphical Model](#)
 - [Execute Model in Web-Browser \(Browser needs WebAssembly support\)](#)
 - [Explanatory Video for PacMan C&C Controller](#)
- Super-Mario
 - graphical C&C Model; layout is automatically generated
 - [Open Graphical Model](#)
 - [Execute Model in Web-Browser \(Browser needs WebAssembly support\)](#)
 - [Explanatory Video for Super-Mario C&C Controller](#)

Screenshots of EmbeddedMontiArcStudio

The screenshot displays the EmbeddedMontiArc development environment. The top window shows a code editor with the following code:

```

1 package de.rwth.armin.modeling.autopilot.common;
2
3 stream Abs for Abs {
4   input: 150 tick 0.1 tick 0.0 tick 0.01 tick 20;
5   output: 100 +/- 0.001 tick 0.1 +/- 0.001 tick 0.0 +/- 0.001 tick 0.01 +/- 0.001 tick 20 +/- 0.001;
6 }
7

```

Below the code editor, the Test Results window shows the following output:

```

-----
TestsForCurrentModel.exe is a catch v2.0.1 host application.
Run with -? for options
-----
de.rwth.armin.modeling.autopilot.common.Abs
-----
C:\Users\vonwenckstern\Documents\emasv1.4.0-final\EmbeddedMontiArcStudio\tests-cpp\test\de_rwth_armin_mo
-----
C:\Users\vonwenckstern\Documents\emasv1.4.0-final\EmbeddedMontiArcStudio\tests-cpp\test\de_rwth_armin_mo
-----
  REQUIRE( component.output <= 100.001 )
  with expansion:
    150.0 <= 100.001
-----
test cases: 1 | 1 failed
assertions: 2 | 1 passed | 1 failed

```

The interface includes a workspace tree on the left, a command palette, and a menu bar at the top.

Integrated Test Environment

Videos

Middleware Plugins.

Coupling EmbeddedMontiArc with different Middlewares.

<p>EmbeddedMontiArc w...</p>	
<p>Simulating several Cars</p>	

Here, we embed the videos mentioned in the paper showing our EmbeddedMontiArc development environment.

<p>EmbeddedMontiArcSt...</p>	
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